

Overview

Target resources and feedstock

Feedstock	Target resources	Potential utilization
Regolith (High land and Mere)	Metals (Aluminum, Magnesium, Iron)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Habitat material• Fuel (Mg)• Electrical components• Mechanical components• Magnetic shielding• Heat sink• Mirror (coating)
	Silicon	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Mirror• Solar panel
	Oxygen	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Fuel• Metabolic needs

Other feedstock, target resource and utilization will be out of scope
(e.g., water, atmosphere, helium3)

Scope of extraction method

Methods	Output	Description
Molten Regolith Electrolysis	Oxygen, Metals, Si	Melt the regolith and use the molten regolith as a supply of ion/electron to conduct electrolysis
Molten Salt Electrolysis	Oxygen, Metals, Si (Each elements can be reduced at different time, but separation method requires new design)	Melt the salt and attach a sintered regolith to the cathode. Use the molten salt as a supply of ion/electron to conduct electrolysis
Acid Leach	Metals, Si	Melt the regolith and use the molten regolith as a supply of ion/electron to conduct electrolysis

MRE

MRE modeling (Schreiner, 2015)

- PhD thesis that utilize computational simulation for MRE
- Heat loss was calculated by the radiative emission from the reactor wall using Multiphysics simulations (conduction and convection heat loss was assumed minimal because it will only be facing the ground and the vacuum)
- Explore with different insulation/refractory thickness and layer numbers (thickness started from 2cm and MLI reached around 100 layers)
- Thermoelectric generator or other heat recovery method was briefly mentioned but was not explored.

Thermophysical properties change during MRE(Humbert, 2022)

- Utilized computational modeling
- Focus was more on the thermophysical properties inside of the reactor and not the heat loss
- Incorporated how regolith thermos properties would change due to heating and electrolysis during the MRE process
- Concluded that convective heat transport is on the same magnitude as conduction due to high viscosity
- Radiation was not included in the model but they mentioned TiO_2 potentially can reduce the radiate heat loss because it can act as opacifier

Joule-heated MRE concept (Laurent 2012)

- One of the early paper about MRE thermal analysis
- Found that above 1000C, thermal radiation dominates heat transfer (optical absorption coefficient strongly affects heat retention)
- Cold startup is a challenge for Joule heating (Electric current brings enough heat) and can cause huge heat loss due to excellent insulation properties. Once it reaches enough temperature, regolith thermal conductivity increases sharply
- Used COMSOL Multiphysics
- modeling

Schneier MRE model

- Multiphysics model
- Included chemical, electrodynamic and thermodynamic physics
- Still almost half of the power is regolith heat loss
- Focused on steady state and briefly looked at the startup process for large scale
- Multi-layer insulation (15 layers), different wall material was explored to mitigate the heat loss

Figure 3-9: The power predictions from the ISRU system model compared to four linear scaling laws from the literature.

Figure 2-12: A side view of the cross-section of the multiphysics simulation of a cylindrical MRE reactor. The primary heat fluxes modeled are shown with different colored arrows, scaled by the same factor.

MRE/Carbothermal reactor heat reuse based on regolith

- Regolith seems to have a great insulation property which potential can reduce the radiative heat loss
- No research has been done
- Schreiner et. al., created a thermophysical property model for lunar regolith which can be used for modeling

Schreiner, Samuel S., et al. "Thermophysical property models for lunar regolith." *Advances in space research* 57.5 (2016): 1209-1222.

Other papers

- Waste heat recovery for solid oxide electrolysis mainly for water electrolysis. Used heat exchangers to transport or store energy (Storaas 2023)
- Explored ideas of transferring the heat to other ISRU or space system (Sonia 2021)

Molten Salt Electrolysis

Molten Salt Electrolysis

- Utilize electrochemical reduction to operate at lower temperature than MRE (still around 800-1200C)
- Common salts are CaCl_2 , LiCl, fluoride and NaCl
- Downside is that it requires consumable such as electrode and addition of salt due to leak and contamination (Rabinot 2025)
- Some parametric modeling has been attempted but not in detail (Hipp 2024)

Jack Robinot, Sylvain Rodat, Stéphane Abanades, Alexis Paillet, Aidan Cowley, Review of in-situ oxygen extraction from lunar regolith with focus on solar thermal and laser vacuum pyrolysis, *Acta Astronautica*, Volume 234, 2025, Pages 242-259, ISSN 0094-5765,

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2025.05.008>.

Hipp, Florian & Guerrero Gonzalez, Francisco Javier. (2024). Development of a parametric sizing model for Molten Salt Electrolysis to coproduce Oxygen and Metals on the Moon.

Experimental work (Schild et al 2025)

- Latest paper from the ESA group that is working on molten salt electrolysis
- Used lunar regolith simulant (LHS-1, Anorthite)
- Require sintering of regolith to attach to the cathode
- High oxygen extraction percentage (95%<)
- Left with a sponged block of slug

Fig. 2. Schematic of molten salt reactor used for electrolysis experiments (left) and photograph of electrode assembly before electrolysis (right).

Table 5. Calculated oxygen extraction and current efficiency for each experiment, compared to results for LMS-1 mare regolith simulant by Meurisse et al. [18].

Experiment	Bulk O content wt. %	Charge passed 10 ³ C	O extraction %	Current efficiency %
LHS-1 A	3.7	264	97	50
LHS-1 B	2.7	270	98	50
Anorth. A	2.5	233	98	58
Anorth. B	1.4	243	99	56
LMS-1 [12]	-	-	85	48

HCl leaching

- Utilize HCl for extracting Aluminum oxide and conduct reduction process focused on Lunar highland regolith
- Use CaCl_2 for molten salt electrolyte to conduct electrolysis for Al_2O_3 to remove oxygen
- Beneficiation required to get anorthite from mixed regolith
- Experimental demonstration that showed >85% concentration of Al
- As a by product, SiO_2 , CaCl_2 can be recovered (no concentration analysis)
- No system level analysis (some energy calculation but were based on experiment)

Jacob N. Ortega, Todd P. Sander, Jeffrey D. Smith, Fateme Rezaei, David J. Bayless, William Schonberg, Daniel S. Stutts, Frank D. Han, Extraction of Aluminum from Lunar Regolith through Molten Salt Electrolysis, Acta Astronautica, Volume 235, 2025, Pages 17-28, ISSN 0094-5765, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2025.04.064>.

Acid leach

H₂SO₄: Metal harvesting overall system (Berggren 2009)

- Extract each oxidized metals (Fe₂O₃, CaO, Al₂O₃, MgO) by using different concentration of sulfuric acid which can be controlled by adding base such as MgO
- In-situ resource on Mars allows to produce H₂SO₄ (Water and MgSO₄) but the paper does not go depth in the production process
- Final potential products are metallic iron, Ca, Al, Mg, Fe₂O₃, concrete, salt-bonded product, sintered product, alkali metal sulfate salt, Silica Glass, manganese and others minor elements
- Recycling of sulfuric acid is possible by recombining H₂O, SO₂ and O₂
- Highlevel system analysis was conducted by estimating each component mass
- Experiment was conducted based on Mars soil simulant for the first step
- 192kg/day soil through

Table 21.7 Hardware Summary.

Component	Mass [kg]
Extraction Column	100
Crystallizer	81
Precipitator	108
Evaporator	108
Acid Regenerator	115
Mg(OH) ₂ Slurry Tank	54
Condenser	62
Vacuum Drying Oven	39
Roasting-Reduction Furnace	165
Electrolyzer	69
Oxygen Liquefaction Module	187
Oxygen Storage System	110
Pneumatic Gas System	15
Instrumentation/Controls/Ancillary	20
Equipment Frames/Supports	62
Total Hardware Mass	1295

Berggren, M., Zubrin, R., Wilson, C., Rose, H., & Carrera, S. (2009). Mars aqueous processing system. *Mars: Prospective energy and material resources* (pp. 563–586). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-9122-8_17

	First	Second	Third	Fourth	Fifth	Sixth	Seventh
Extr	27.5	33.0	32.0	1.5	10.0	0.0	20.0
Stag	32.9	73.8	79.1	50.8	14.1	12.6	36.0

H2SO4: Acid production

- Because SO₃ is unstable and can easily be converted to SO₂+O₂, t
- Main chemical reaction to produce sulfuric acid. FeSO₄ acts as a catalyst to form sulfuric acid

- Due to extreme endothermic reaction, 1:1 SO₃ + H₂O reaction will cause evaporation of H₂SO₄ which complicates and makes the process difficult (Can be solved by having large amount of H₂SO₄ absorbs this heat)
- If we just cool the vapor, we get SO₂ and O₂

King, M., Moats, M., Davenport, W. G., & King, M. J. (2005). *Sulfuric acid manufacture: Analysis, control and optimization*. Elsevier.

H2SO4: Mineral based metal leaching analysis(Seamus 2021)

- Study looked into the mineology to assess which mineral can be leached based on H2SO4
- Uses thermal decomposition for produced sulfates
- High-level thermal analysis and recoverable resource poetential was calculated for Lunar, Mars and asteroid regolith
- No system level analysis

Seamus L. Anderson, Eleanor K. Sansom, Patrick M. Shober, Benjamin A.D. Hartig, Hadrien A.R. Devillepoix
 The proposed Silicate-Sulfuric Acid Process: Mineral processing for In Situ Resource Utilization (ISRU),
 Acta Astronautica, Volume 188, 2021, Pages 57-63, ISSN 0094-5765, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2021.05.001>

Table 2

Generalized thermal decomposition reactions for produced sulfates. The Oxides described are: Al_2O_3 :Alumina). The positive values attained for ΔG° indicate that heat-energy is required. The reactions are collectively referred to as **Reaction 8**.

Reactants		Sulfur Dioxide (g)	Oxygen (g)
Sulfate (s)			
2 FeSO ₄	→	2 SO ₂	½ O ₂
2 MgSO ₄		2 SO ₂	O ₂
2 CaSO ₄		2 SO ₂	O ₂
Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃		3 SO ₂	¾ O ₂

Potential research gaps

- Molten salt electrolysis (CaCl₂) vs MRE on Moon and Mars environment
 - Step1: Modeling the reactor using COMSOL (for MRE, we can reference Schreiner 2015) -> start after step4 to articulate the process, should be able to justify, more from demand side, before comsol
 - Step2: Vary size and geometry for processing and power efficiency (maybe without solution)
 - Step3: Apply some heat recovery method to measure the heat efficiency
 - Step4: Estimate the total power and payload mass to make a comprehensive comparison
 - (Step5: Would power requirement and performance change if we use different heating method such as sunlight based heating) (again, before comsol)
 - Specification
 - (There are other method such as carbothermal, hydrogen reduction and acid leach but will keep it out of scope for this research or only address in a high level)
- Hypothesis
 - MSE has an advantage in a small scale but MRE starts to have an advantage once the plant scales up
 - Heat reuse significantly improves the MRE performance but not MSE
 - Operational complexity gives a huge advantage for MRE -> Harry jones 2021, component number, discounted value but should be included in the analysis, quasi, both method should have the same fidelity and resolution to do a fair comparison
 - Mar and moon will have different thermal behaviour due to different gravity and the presence and absence of atmosphere (also different energy production method which leads to different energy supply characteristics)

Solar panel production

Solar cell structure

Sunlight

Anti reflective coating	Avoids reflection of sunlight. SiO ₂ thin film through PVD/CVD
Front contact	Transparent or a grid with conductive material. Al is likely the best in-situ material
n-type Si	Si doped with small amount of material with one extra valence electron. Likely require the doping material from Earth (P, As, Sb, Bi etc.)
p-type Si	Si doped with small amount of material with one less valence electron. Al can be used for the doping
Back contact	Any conductive material that does not damage the Si. Al is the top candidate, potentially also Fe

Solar panel production flow chart

High purity silicon production

NASA paper states this process can be replaced by heating in a vacuum resulting in 5N purity

First purification step
(98% purity)

Second purification step (99.9999% 6N)

Crystallization process

Mono crystal growth step
(higher efficiency but difficult to make)

Multi crystal growth step
(Easier to make but lower efficiency)

MRE based solar panel production assessment (only power balance)

Parameter	Case1	Case2	Case3
Regolith	Highlands	Highlands	Highlands
Solar panel efficiency	5%	5%	10%
Daytime	50%	100%	100%
Dust	70%	100%	100%
PV thickness (mm)	20	20	20
Glass thickness	10	10	10
Breakeven (days)	6820	2390	1190

Acid leach + Carbothermal reduction

Method	Energy required per 1kg-Si
MRE	200 MJ
Carbothermal	25 MJ

- Based on enthalpy calculation, can expect 90% reduction of energy compare to MRE (note mre takes into account of different factor such as heat loss)

Radiation, heat and MMDO degradation assessment

- Mostly meteorites some secondary ejecta
- Extreme heat depending on the location
- Radiation exposure degrades the cell

Generating and storing power on the moon using in situ resources (Alex Ellery)

- Comprehensive review of solar light based power system leveraging ISRU
- Argues solar photovoltaics are unsuitable
 - Degradation due to radiation exposure
 - Low efficiency (states it will be around 5%)
 - High temperature during day time
- Propose solar concentrators as an alternative
 - Use Fresnel lens or parabolic mirror to concentrate the sun light
 - Can create fused silica (requires removing FeO from anorthite)
- Conversion from light to heat is required
 - Argues photon-enhanced thermionic has the best properties (conversion efficiency of around 70%)
 - Normal thermionic has efficiency of 30%
- Propose flywheel for power storage
 - Electro mechanical energy storage is available due to less friction

Thermoelectric generator (TEG)

- Uses temperature difference to electrical current / voltage
- Robust and no moving parts (static system) leads to longer lifetime
- Leverage the extreme temperature on the lunar surface

Back of an envelope calculation

- Zeeback effect

Iron disilicate thermoelectric generator production based on lunar regolith

- Most common TEG material is alloy of Bi and Te which does not exist on the Moon.
- There are mainly two options
 1. Bring the TEG and make the heat sink based on regolith
 2. Produce the TEG on the surface
- For ISRU production, there are two material options
 - Iron Disilicide (FeSi_2)
 - Magnesium Silicide (Mg_2Si)
- As same as solar array, wires and dust mitigation is required
- Upside is it does not require the purity that is required for solar cell

Power system mass breakdown

- Based on the ISS system, photovoltaic mass is around 24%
- To minimize the launch mass and leverage ISRU, other elements should also be addressed
- Mast and some electrical equipment (such as wires) can be manufactured in-situ

TABLE 20-7 Mass Breakdown of a Solar Array (International Space Station's Photovoltaic Power Module) The photovoltaic blanket contributes 25% of the system mass; array plus structure is half the system's mass

Element	Mass (kg)	Fraction (%)
Photovoltaic blanket	890	24.0
Mast	330	8.8
Gimbal	540	14.5
Electrical equipment	610	16.6
Thermal control	730	19.6
Miscellaneous integration	610	16.5
Total, not including: batteries, charge/discharge unit	3710	100

Potential gaps

- Regolith sintering base parabolic mirror
- Thermal analysis for the thermal electric generation especially around the south pole (determines the accuracy required for the mirror or lenses)
- MMOD and radiation endurance for the solar panel (might give implication that in-situ manufacturing is almost essential)

Solar panel In-situ production

- Assumption
 - Efficiency = 5% (Freundlich2005)
 - No light production during night
 - Dust relevant efficiency drop = -30%
 - Light angle is 90 degrees
 - All silicon is provided by MRE by product
 - Doping material is provided from Earth especially for n-type
- Result:
 - $5.4e11$ W worth of solar panel can be produced
 - Total of $9.2e8$ m² needs to be covered (similar area size as Dallas)
 - If the panel is fixed, the efficiency will drop by another ~60%

Mirror In-situ production

- Can be produced from Si based glass and Al based layer
- Production it self is not difficult (just Si rich regolith sintering and small amount of aluminum)
- But adjusting the angle as the sun moves might be a challenge since we need to produce the motor or equivalent system
- Possibly can explore just using aluminum foil but requires careful design to fight back the wind

Schleppi, J., Gibbons, J., Groetsch, A., Buckman, J., Cowley, A., & Bennett, N. (2019). Manufacture of glass and mirrors from lunar regolith simulant. *Journal of Materials Science*, 54(5), 3726–3747.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-018-3119-7>

Memo

- 0.55×10^4 kg silicon
- 10000kg O₂ /year
- 35kW